

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT INCUBATION PERIODS, TEMPERATURE, RELATIVE HUMIDITY AND DIFFERENT CONCENTRATION OF SUCROSE SOLUTION ON THE UREDOSPORE GERMINATION OF *Cerotelium fici* (Cast.) Arth. CAUSING RUST DISEASE ON FIG (*Ficus carica* L.)

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Abstract

Fig (*Ficus carica*) is a dryland horticulture crop with significant export potential and good economic rewards. Rust caused by *Cerotelium fici* (Cast.) Arth. is one of the major fig disease that cause significant losses in the fig crop. The *in vitro* studies regarding spore germination studies revealed that the maximum uredospores germination (78.55 %) observed at 30 hours of incubation. The optimum temperature for uredospore germination found was 25 °C after 24 hrs of incubation at which the maximum germination (79.65%) was observed. Relative humidity has showed maximum influence on the uredospore germination with highest germination per cent (77.73%) at 100 per cent. The uredospores germinated at maximum rate in 2 per cent sucrose solution.

Key words: Fig, rust, *Cerotelium fici*, *in vitro*, germination, incubation period, temperature, relative humidity, sucrose solution.

Introduction

Fig (*Ficus carica* L.) is an important deciduous fruit crop grown in tropical and subtropical countries including India. It comes under Moraceae family. The name *Carica* comes from its origin place Carica in Asia Minor i.e. Mediterranean region (Starr *et al.*, 2003). In India, total fig area under cultivation is 5904 ha with the production of 14,939.95 tons, mostly with average productivity of 2503 kg/ha during the year 2022 (FAO, 2022). Out of all the states, Maharashtra is the top state, with Karnataka and Uttar Pradesh following closely behind. Pune, in Maharashtra, is the main producer of figs in the state.

The fig yield in Maharashtra is affected by frequency of multiple harmful diseases which affect the crop at various growth phases. Fig crop is infected by number of diseases caused by bacteria, viruses and fungus that includes ig rust (*Cerotelium fici*) anthracnose (*Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*), Armillaria rot (*Armillaria mellea*), bacterial canker (*Pseudomonas fici*), blight disease (*Ceratocystis fimbriata*), leaf spots (*Cylindrocladium scoparium* and *Cercospora fici*), aerial web blight (*Rhizoctonia solani*), sooty mold (*Capnodium spp.*), fruit rot (*Phytophthora palmivora*), rhizopus rot (*Rhizopus stolonifer*), fig mosaic (fig mosaic virus), etc. are the common diseases observed on fig (Bose and Mitra, 2002).

Fig rust is one of the most important disease that causes higher losses and is major obstacle in the cultivation of fig. The rust fungi is obligate in nature and only survives on the living plants. And also spread of the disease occurs through the spores of fungi. Uredospores of rust are major cause of primary and secondary infection of rust. Uredospores spread through the wind, rain splash, insects and by humans. After getting favourable environmental conditions on the host surface uredospores germinate and causes disease to the healthy fig plant. To manage disease effectively it is important to study the epidemiology of rust disease. Also it is important to study germination of rust spores to take protective and curative measures. Therefore, the spore germination studies of fig rust are done in *in-vitro* condition and effect

of different incubation periods, temperature, relative humidity and different concentration of sucrose solution on the uredospore germination of rust (*Cerotelium fici*) is evaluated and presented in this article.

Material and Methods

In vitro evaluation experiments were conducted at Department of Plant Pathology, College of Agriculture, Pune during year 2023-24. The *C. fici* uredospores samples were collected from naturally infected plants in the fig orchards, All India Coordinated Research Project on Fig and Custard Apple, Jadhavwadi, Tal: Purandar, Dist: Pune.

Effect of incubation periods on germination of uredospores of *Cerotelium fici* at 25 ± 1 °C

Uredospore of *C. fici* were collected from diseased plant by tapping of infected leaf from the upper surface. These spores were put on cavity slide with drop of water. The cavity slides were kept in the petridishes lined with blotting paper and then incubated at room temperature (25±1 °C) at different time intervals. The per cent germination of uredospore was recorded after 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21, 24, 27 and 30 hours of incubation. Uredospores with the germ tubes longer than the uredospore radius/ half of the width were considered as germinated. There were three slides for each treatment and per cent germination was calculated based on count of ten microscopic fields for each treatment.

Effect of different relative humidity on germination of uredospores of *C. fici*

The procedure followed for studying the relative humidity requirement for spore germination was similar to the one explained earlier. The slides were incubated for 24 hrs at different relative humidity levels viz., 60, 65, 70, 75, 80, 85, 90, 95 and 100 per cent. These relative humidity levels were maintained in dessicator using different concentrations of H₂SO₄. Then per cent germination of uredospores was calculated. Three replications were maintained for each treatment.

Concentration of H ₂ SO ₄ (%)	RH at 25°C (%)
38	60
36	65
33	70
30	75
27	80
23	85
18	90
11	95
0	100

Effect of different sucrose concentration on germination of uredospores of *C. fici*.

Uredospore of *C. fici* were collected by tapping of infected leaf from upper surface. These spores were put on cavity slide with 0.5, 1, 2 and

3% concentrations of sucrose solution and distilled water. The cavity slides were kept in petridishes lined with blotting paper and then incubated at room temperature (25 ± 1°C) for about 24 hrs. The per

cent germination was worked out by observing at ten microscopic fields in each replication.

Result and Discussion:

Effect of incubation periods on germination of uredospores of *Cerotelium fici* at 25 ± 1 °C

The results (Table 1) indicated that, the germination of uredospores initiated at 6 hours of incubation (8.88 %) further germination of uredospores increases with time to more than 50% germination after 15 hours (51.25 %). Subsequent increase in germination observed in

advanced period, the maximum germination (78.55 %) observed at 30 hours of incubation, which is followed by 27 hours (76.60 %) and 24 hours (74.83%) respectively which are statistically at par with each other.

These results are in agreement with Sreekantappa (2000) who recorded maximum germination of uredospores of *Cerotelium fici* obtained after 24 hrs of incubation which was at par with 48 hrs of incubation. Dey *et al.*, (2015) also obtained same results of uredospores germination in corn rust (*Puccinia sorghi*).

Table 1 Effect of incubation periods on uredospore germination of *Cerotelium fici*

Sr. No.	Incubation period (hrs)	Germination (%)
1	6	8.88 (17.29)
2	9	21.25 (27.44)
3	12	32.08 (34.48)
4	15	51.25 (45.70)
5	18	59.02 (50.19)
6	21	67.70 (55.36)
7	24	74.83 (59.87)
8	27	76.60 (61.05)
9	30	78.55 (62.39)
	SE(m)±	1.10
	C.D. (5%)	3.28
	C.V. (%)	4.13

Figures in parenthesis are arcsine values

Effect of different temperature regimes on the germination of uredospores of *C. fici*

The temperature is major factor influencing the germination of uredospores of rust of fig. The spores were incubated at different temperature regimes viz., 5, 10, 20, 25, 30, 35°C for 24 hours and

results were depicted in the Table 2. No germination of uredospores were seen at 5°C. The germination starts at 10°C (27.25%) which increases gradually with temperature to reach maximum germination at 25°C (79.65 %) and then it decreases with further increases in temperature to 35°C (29.00 %).

Table 2. Effect of different temperature regimes on uredospore germination of *C. fici*

Sr. No.	Temperature (°C)	Germination count (%)
1	5	0.00 (0.00)
2	10	27.25 (31.45)
3	20	42.74 (40.79)
4	25	79.65 (63.17)
5	30	70.10 (56.84)
6	35	29.00 (32.53)
	SE(m)±	0.85
	C.D. (5%)	2.54
	C.V. (%)	4.54

Figures in parenthesis are arcsine values

These results are in conformity with Sreekantappa (2000) who reported temperature range of 25° - 30 °C was ideal for uredospore germination of *Cerotelium fici* causing fig rust. Similar results were obtained by Anusha *et al.*, (2018) as maximum uredospores germination of *C. fici* at 25° C after 24 hrs of incubation.

Effect of different relative humidity on germination of uredospores of *C. fici*

As the temperature, relative humidity is also one of the important factor which influence the germination of rust uredospores. The spores were incubated at different relative humidity viz., 60, 65, 70, 75, 80,

85, 90, 95 and 100 % for 24 hours. The results are documented in the Table 3. The germination of uredospores started at 60% relative humidity (10.33%). Maximum germination is recorded at 100% relative humidity (77.73%) which is followed by 95% (70.48 %) and 90 % (66.20%). It is seen that germination of uredospores increases gradually with increase in relative humidity.

These results were similar to Sreekantappa (2000) who recorded maximum germination of uredospores of *Cerotelium fici* at 100 per cent relative humidity (RH) and stated relative humidity in the range of 88-100 per cent was most suited for uredospore germination.

Anusha *et al.*, (2018) also found similar results with maximum uredospore germination (60.38%) at 100 per cent relative humidity and no germination was observed at 65 per cent relative humidity.

Table 3 Effect of relative humidity on uredospore germination after 24 hrs of incubation.

Sr. No.	Relative Humidity (%)	Germination count (%)
1	60	10.33 (18.74)
2	65	22.52 (28.31)
3	70	24.33 (29.54)
4	75	50.23 (45.12)
5	80	53.47 (46.97)
6	85	59.83 (50.65)
7	90	66.20 (54.43)
8	95	70.48 (57.07)
9	100	77.73 (61.84)
	SE(m) \pm	0.42
	C.D. (5%)	1.26
	C.V. (%)	1.68

Figures in parenthesis are arcsine values

Effect of different sucrose concentration on germination of uredospores of *C. fici*.

For profused and early germination of uredospores it requires several ideal conditions such as ideal substrate, optimal temperature, congenial relative humidity, *etc.* In the present experiment germination of uredospores at different sucrose concentrations *viz.* 0.5, 1.0, 2.0 and 3.0% were studied for 24 hours and the results were depicted in Table 4. The germination of uredospores were least at 0.5% concentration of sucrose (31.27%). It was observed that per cent germination of uredospores increased to 51.28 % at 1.0% sucrose concentration to reach maximum germination of 79.89 % at 2.0%

concentration (Plate 4 d),. However, the germination of uredospores decreases considerably to 69.80% with further increase in the concentration of sucrose solution to 3.0%.

The results indicated that uredospores of *C. fici* require nutrition for germination and the findings of this investigations are in agreement with Naresh (2007) who obtained the maximum uredospore germination of rust of fig caused by *C. fici* (Cast.) Arth. under 2 per cent sucrose solution (80.60 %) which was reduced to 69.66% at 3.0 per cent sucrose solution. But these findings are in controversy with the findings of Sreekantappa (2000) who got maximum per cent of uredospore germination (84.66 %) in 3 per cent sucrose solution.

Table 4 Effect of different sucrose concentration on germination of uredospores of *C. fici*.

Sr. No.	Substrate	Conc (%)	Germination count (%)
1	Sucrose solution	0.5	31.27 (33.98)
2	Sucrose solution	1.0	51.28 (45.72)
3	Sucrose solution	2.0	79.89 (63.35)
4	Sucrose solution	3.0	69.80 (56.65)
		SE(m) \pm	0.51
		C.D. (5%)	1.55
		C.V. (%)	2.29

Figures in parenthesis are arcsine values

Conclusion:

Spore germination studies revealed that the maximum uredospores germination (78.55 %) observed at 30 hours of incubation. The optimum temperature for uredospore germination found was 25° C after 24 hrs of incubation at which the maximum germination (79.65%) was observed. Relative humidity has showed maximum influence on the uredospore germination with highest germination per cent (77.73%) at 100 per cent. The uredospores germinated at maximum rate in 2 per cent sucrose sucrose.

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